

The Pfeiffer Effect, Outer-Sphere Complexation, and the Absolute Configuration of Coordination Compounds

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Introduction

The Pfeiffer Effect^{1, 2} is the change in optical rotation which occurs when a racemic mixture of certain dissymmetric coordination compounds (optically labile complexes) is added to a solution of an optically active compound (the "environment" compound). It has been observed^{3, 6} to occur with racemic mixtures of optically labile coordination compounds in water solutions (and in a few non-aqueous solvents) with a variety of optically active organic environment compounds. The magnitude of the Effect is directly proportional to the concentrations of the complex and the optically active environment substance in normal concentration ranges^{4, 5}.

Nature of the Pfeiffer effect

It has been postulated by Dwyer and Gyarfás⁷ that the Effect occurs because of an *equilibrium displacement* process. That is, it is proposed that the two enantiomers of a racemic mixture of an optically labile complex in solution are in equilibrium with each other, and, in an optically inactive environment, the equilibrium constant is 1 (eq. 1). However, if the environment is made

optically active, then the equilibrium is shifted, thus changing the constant to something other than 1 (eq. 2). This proposal has

been supported by several experiments^{3-6, 8, 9} including optical rotatory dispersion and circular dichroism measurements, optical resolution experiments, racemization studies, and other work.

For example, it has been demonstrated⁵ that the o. r. d. and c. d. spectra of an optically pure sample of a coordination compound are the same as those

taken with a racemic mixture of the complex, after it has undergone the Pfeiffer Effect. Further, it has been shown⁸ that the Pfeiffer Effect can be utilized to resolve racemic mixtures of certain optically labile complexes, and that these enantiomers racemize at the same rate as optically pure forms of them.

The influence of pH on the Pfeiffer Effect

It has been noticed by Nordquist¹⁰ and Ahmad¹¹ that pH has a pronounced effect on the magnitude and rate of appearance of the Pfeiffer Effect. For example, for the system D,L-[Ni(*o*-phen)₃]²⁺ with aqueous (-)_Dmalic acid, the magnitude of the Pfeiffer Effect is decreased and the rate of appearance of the Effect is increased markedly with increasing pH of the solution. This was not expected, since conversion of malic acid to monohydrogen malate (or malate) anion was expected to increase the magnitude of the interaction between the complex and the environment compound, which was expected to result in enhancement of the magnitude of the Effect. However, it is now possible to explain this observation on the basis of the nature of the interaction between the two species (*vide infra*).

The Pfeiffer Effect and the Absolute Configuration of Organic Compounds

It was noticed¹¹ that the Pfeiffer Effect on D, L-[Co(*o*-phen)₃]²⁺ in the presence of aqueous (-)_Dmalic acid and aqueous (-)_Dtartaric acid resulted in enrichment of the enantiomer of the complex which has a negative Cotton Effect at 450 nm. (the (-)_D enantiomer of the complex). It was also noticed¹¹ that this same enantiomer was enriched in aqueous (+)_Dcinchonine hydrochloride. It was concluded, therefore, that these three organic compounds must have the same absolute configuration. Consequently, several organic environment substances of known absolute configuration have been utilized in Pfeiffer Effect studies of the cobalt (II) -*ortho*-phenanthroline

complex¹² in an effort to determine whether this Effect can be utilized to predict the absolute configuration of organic compounds. That is, those optically active organic environment compounds which result in enrichment of the (-)_D enantiomer of the complex during the appearance of the Pfeiffer Effect are predicted to possess the "S" absolute configuration, and *vice versa*. Table I shows the results of these predictions for organic compounds.

TABLE I—THE PREDICTION OF THE ABSOLUTE CONFIGURATION OF ORGANIC COMPOUNDS UTILIZING THE PFEIFFER EFFECT

Compounds	Predicted Absolute Configuration	Observed Absolute Configuration
(-) _D Malic Acid	S	S
(-) _D Tartaric Acid	S	S
(+) _D Aspartic Acid	S	S
(+) _D Alanine	S	S
(+) _D Tartaric Acid	R	R
(+) _D Malic Acid	R	R
(-) _D Mandelic Acid	R	R

The Pfeiffer Effect and the Absolute Configuration of Dissymmetric Coordination Compounds

Experiments were then undertaken to determine whether it would be possible to predict the absolute configuration of dissymmetric complex inorganic compounds via the Pfeiffer Effect. It was noted^{11, 12} that S(-)_Dmalic acid resulted in enrichment of the

(-)_D [Ni(*o*-phen)₃]²⁺ enantiomer, which has been shown to have a Δc_3 absolute configuration¹³.

It was postulated, therefore, that S(-)_Dmalic acid would produce the Δc_3 enantiomer in excess during the Pfeiffer Effect on any racemic complex. An experiment was performed on *D,L*-[Fe(*o*-phen)₃]²⁺ using S(-)_Dmalic acid as the environment substance, and enrichment of the (+)_D enantiomer of the complex resulted. It was supposed, therefore, that this complex should have the Δc_3 absolute configuration, and this was verified in the literature¹⁴. Table II gives the predicted and observed absolute configurations of some dissymmetric complexes with various organic environment compounds.

The Nature of the Pfeiffer Effect Interactions

The nature of the interactions between the environment substance and the dissymmetric complex in solution has been studied by the research group of the author for some time. It has been known for some time that the environment substance does not displace a ligand from the complex during the appearance of the Pfeiffer Effect. The absorption spectrum of the complex indicates that it retains its structural integrity during the Pfeiffer Effect. However, it has also been known for some time that hydrogen bonding is possible between hydroxyl hydrogens and aromatic systems¹⁵⁻¹⁸. It is therefore postulated that the basic interaction of the Pfeiffer Effect is hydrogen bonding between the organic environment substance and the complex's pi electrons of the aromatic ring systems. The most effective type of hydrogen bonding to aromatic systems has been shown¹⁵⁻¹⁸ to be of the "head-on" type, in which the plane of the ring systems is perpendicular to the O-H line.

TABLE II—THE PREDICTION OF THE ABSOLUTE CONFIGURATION OF DISSYMMETRIC COORDINATION COMPOUNDS UTILIZING THE PFEIFFER EFFECT

Complex	Environment Substance	Enriched Enantiomer of Complex	Predicted Absolute Configuration	Observed Absolute Configuration
[Ni(<i>o</i> -phen) ₃] ²⁺	S(-) _D Malic Acid	(-) _D	Δc_3	Δc_3
[Ni(<i>o</i> -phen) ₃] ²⁺	S(+) _D Aspartic Acid	"	"	"
[Fe(<i>o</i> -phen) ₃] ²⁺	S(+) _D Aspartic Acid	(+) _D	"	"
[Fe(<i>o</i> -phen) ₃] ²⁺	S(-) _D Malic Acid	"	"	"

Using Dreiding models, it can be seen that $S(-)_D$ malic acid can hydrogen-bond more effectively than $R(+)_D$ malic acid to two "propeller" blades (*o*-phen rings) of the Δ_{e_3} enantiomer of the complex. There will be fewer non-bonded interactions, and better "head-on" hydrogen-bonding in this case (the OH groups on carbons 1 and 2 are hydrogen-bonded to one ring and the OH on carbon 4 is hydrogen-bonded to a second ring). The fixing of two rings (or "blades" of a 3-bladed propeller) automatically fixes the absolute configuration of the third. Thus, for the equilibrium described by equation (2), the "L" enantiomer is unable to convert to the "D" form as easily as the "D" is able to convert to the "L", because the "L" form is stabilized or fixed to some extent by hydrogen-bonding with $S(-)_D$ malic acid. This drives the equilibrium in the direction shown.

This proposed mechanism also explains the observation that the magnitude of the Pfeiffer Effect is significantly diminished with an increase in pH of the system. Both OH protons of the carboxyl groups of the malic acid are necessary for the hydrogen bonding to occur, since the *ortho*-phenanthroline ring systems cannot provide usable protons for this purpose. An increase in pH will remove these protons, resulting in a diminution of the Pfeiffer Effect, as observed.

Outer-Sphere Complexation and the Absolute Configuration of Dissymmetric Coordination Compounds

Bhatnagar and Kirschner (19) reported that no Cotton Effect occurs in a solution of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+}$ ($-)_D$ tartrate⁻ in water. Mason and Norman (20) reported a strong negative circular dichroism peak in the visible region for this system, if the concentration of tartrate (diethyltartrate) is 400 times that of the metal complex. This has been verified by the author

and Munir²¹, and has also been found to occur for the $[\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+}$ complex. It was decided to determine whether this interaction occurs with D, L - $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$ and a 400-fold excess of $(+)_D$ tartaric acid. It was observed that a strong²¹ negative Cotton Effect does indeed appear, but at 460nm., and not at the absorption peak or CD peak of the optically active complex $(+)_D[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$ (486 nm.).

It was found to be possible to utilize this effect to predict the absolute configuration of optically stable, dissymmetric complex inorganic compounds. By comparing the circular dichroism spectra of each enantiomer (separately) of $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$ in a 400-fold excess of $(+)_D$ tartaric acid (and, later, in a 400-fold excess of $(-)_D$ malic acid), with the circular dichroism spectra of the pure enantiomers in aqueous solution, it can be seen that the environment compound (in the tartaric acid case) interacts more strongly with the $(+)_D$ Δ_{e_3} enantiomer of the complex than the opposite isomer. During this interaction between the $(+)_D$ enantiomer of tartaric acid and the $(+)_D$ enantiomer of $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$ the circular dichroism spectrum is diminished (less positive) to a greater extent than the circular dichroism spectrum of the interaction between the $(+)_D$ enantiomer of tartaric acid and the $(-)_D$ enantiomer of the complex is diminished (less negative). The greater difference occurs at 460 nm., which explains the observed circular dichroism spectrum of the racemic complex with a 400-fold excess of $(+)_D$ tartaric acid.

Further, it is postulated that the enantiomer which has the stronger interaction with $R(+)_D$ tartaric acid is the Δ_{e_3} isomer, and the enantiomer which shows the stronger interaction with an environment substance of "S" absolute configuration will be the Δ_{e_3} isomer. This was confirmed with $S(-)_D$ malic acid, which produces a circular dichroism spectrum with D, L - $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$ in water with a positive peak at 460 nm. (see Table III).

TABLE III—THE PREDICTION OF THE ABSOLUTE CONFIGURATION OF A DISSYMMETRIC COORDINATION COMPOUND UTILIZING OUTER-SPHERE COMPLEXATION.

Compound	Environment Substance	Complex Enantiomer of Stronger Interaction	Predicted Absolute Configuration	Observed Absolute Configuration
$[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$	$R(+)_D$ Tartaric Acid	$(+)_D$ Isomer	Δ_{e_3}	Δ_{e_3}
$[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$	$S(-)_D$ Malic Acid	$(-)_D$ Isomer	Δ_{e_3}	Δ_{e_3}

Fig. 1. Proposed Outer-Sphere Complexation of (+)_D Tartaric Acid with [Co(NH₃)₆]³⁺

The Nature of the Outer-Sphere Interaction

It is proposed that hydrogen-bonding is also responsible for the interaction of environment compounds with optically stable, dissymmetric complexes. However, this hydrogen bonding does not involve pi electron clouds of aromatic ring systems. Instead, it is proposed that the hydrogen bonding occurs through the oxygen atoms of the environment compound and the nitrogen and hydrogen of the²¹ ligands (see Fig 1). This would result in optically active carbon atoms being incorporated into the ring system of the chromophore of the complex, which would explain the conversion of the optically inactive absorption band of [Co(NH₃)₆]³⁺ into an optically active one. It is also proposed that an organic environment compound of one absolute configuration (e.g., "S") can attain closer approach to one enantiomer than the other of an optically active complex e.g., Δ_{e₃} (-)_D [Co(en)₃]³⁺, which would account for the stronger interaction between this pair than between the "R" enantiomer of the environment substance and the Δ_{e₃} enantiomer of the complex. Further experiments are underway to test this proposal.

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